

Using mulch to increase Ecosystem Services of *Phaseolus beans* and reduce weed pressure

Problem

In organic horticulture, weed management poses a major challenge and can significantly affect yield and consequently crop economic viability. For instance, fresh bean production is highly labour-intensive, with weed control relying largely on manual labour. As a result, weed pressure can make organic production economically unviable.

Solution

Mulching is a well-established method for weed suppression; however, its use in larger-scale production is often neglected because of challenges related to soil cultivation (e.g. lack of adequate equipment to cut the mulch residues) and potential pest problems (e.g. fungal diseases or insect pests or rodents which can overwinter under the mulch). Experiences from the Hungarian biointensive fixed-bed system demonstrate that applying straw mulch at sowing can completely suppress weed growth.

Benefits

By using straw mulch, weed pressure is significantly reduced, thereby improving the economic viability of fresh bean production. In addition, the practice delivers multiple soil-related ecological benefits: soil temperature is moderated, straw contributes organic matter to the topsoil, and early-stage soil cover protects the surface from erosion and drying. Together, these effects enhance soil ecosystem services—such as erosion control and nutrient cycling—and contribute to improved overall soil health.

Practical recommendations

- **Sowing and straw application (Fig. 1A):** Straw mulch can be applied either before sowing, followed by direct drilling of the beans, or after sowing by covering with straw. In spring sowings, straw mulch may lower soil temperatures and therefore slow germination; this should be considered when timing application.
- **Mulching (Fig. 1B):** Apply a straw mulch layer of at least 5 cm and up to a maximum of 20 cm. Chopped straw is the easiest to apply and provides the most uniform and effective soil coverage. If necessary, the mulch layer can be renewed during the growing season, preferably before crop canopy closure.

Applicability box

Theme

Mulching to decrease weed pressure

Keywords

Mulch, *Phaseolus* bean, weed pressure, ecosystem services

Context

Central Europe

Application time

During vegetation period of bean from sowing till harvesting

Required time

A few hours to apply mulch depending on the surface of beds.

Period of impact

Cultivation period, soil improvement for next crop

Equipment

Straw mulch, compost, straw shredder/chopper

Best in

Biointensive fixed bed system, market gardening, organic horticulture

- **Termination:** After harvest, the straw mulch can be terminated together with crop residues. Best practice is to chop the residues and either leave them on the soil surface or incorporate them shallowly into the upper soil layer.

Fig. 1. A. Right Panel: Applying straw during sowing of *Phaseolus beans*; B. Left Panel: Straw mulch can efficiently suppress weeds in biointensive fixed bed systems. Photos: Alfréd Szilágyi, Agri Kulti

Further information

Video

- Using Straw Mulch for Weed Control: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=htzJxrrf4_E (English)

Further reading

- Liang, M., Chen, L., Chen, G., Zhao, Y., Liu, G., Sun, E., ... Qu, P. (2025). Protective effects of straw mulching on soil health and function: a review. *Environmental Pollutants and Bioavailability*, 37(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/26395940.2025.2533900>

Useful Weblinks

- Mulching in organic agriculture: <https://teca.apps.fao.org/en/technologies/8365/>
- Organic Mulching Materials for Weed Management: <https://eorganic.org/node/4871>
- The organic gardening way: long-term sustainability and abundant harvests in one garden: <https://www.biogarden365.com/en/organic-gardening-biointensive-farming-guide/>

About this practice abstract

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